

(просторового) розвитку з використанням всього набору інструментів регіональної політики [1, с. 211-214].

В результаті проведених в НУ «Одеська політехніка» та Ізмаїльському державному гуманітарному університеті досліджень проведено визначення стратегії розвитку транскордонного сиро-еколого-рекреаційного кластеру «Фрумушика-Нова» [3, с. 346-355]. Сьогодні Фрумушика-Нова – це центр етнографічного, сільського, зеленого туризму та сімейного відпочинку. На його території розташовується найбільший в Європі вівчарський комплекс з вирощування овець каракульської породи; найвищий гранітний пам'ятник України, внесений до Національного реєстру рекордів України; етнографічний музей просто неба; центр сімейного відпочинку; парк скульптур, міні-зоосад.

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PECULIARITIES OF PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT UNDER THE MARTIAL LAW

The martial law in Ukraine made companies reform many internal processes as soon as possible. Due to the quick adaptation to new realities and the search for alternatives, companies could continue and effectively manage their activities, including interaction with their personnel.

In this regard, the issue of personnel management becomes especially important.

Personnel management is the organization of work with personnel documents on issues of acceptance, transfer, dismissal, accounting, attestation, training, advanced training, internship, and pension provision of employees. It determines the specificity of the production relations between the employer and employees within an organization.

In peacetime, keeping personnel records was a rather ordinary task, quite understandable and predictable. Under the martial law, the companies had many problems regarding the further documentary support of production relations. They included drawing up and exchanging personnel documents, communicating with employees, including submitting applications to the employer, and confirming employee orders.

On March 24, 2022, the Law of Ukraine "On the organization of labor relations under martial law" [1] entered into force, which defines the organization of personnel records and the temporary special conditions of archival storage of personnel documents.

Article 7 of the Law stipulates that the procedure for the organization of personnel records and archival storage of personnel documents in areas of active hostilities during martial law is determined by the employer independently, on the condition of keeping reliable records of the work performed by employees and labor costs [1].

In the conditions of martial law, the procedure for exchanging documents related to the organization of production relations is complicated. This is because some employees emigrated to other regions of Ukraine or abroad. In this context, the process of exchanging personnel documents can be organized electronically, in particular, by signing electronic documents with electronic signatures.

To simplify personnel management and formalize personnel procedures during martial law, employers can organize personnel management as follows:

- determine procedures and means of communication between employees and employers;
- approval of internal acts (procedures and instructions) for the unification of personnel management under the martial law. For example, this is a list of documents whose validity should be suspended, the procedure for submitting and sending applications, the procedure for distributing orders throughout the organization, the procedure for providing work books in the case of dismissal, etc.

At the beginning of the introduction of martial law in Ukraine, employers had many questions about reforming relations with employees; but within three months, many changes to the labor legislation of Ukraine were adopted. However, the optimization process is still ongoing. Currently, there is no universal way of exchanging documents related to personnel management. Considering all the requirements of the legislation, each employer must determine the procedure for the support of production relations during martial law.

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